

FTC Challenges Improper Listings on FDA Pharmaceutical Patent Registry

Issue/problem

US Pharmaceutical firms often improperly list drug patents in the US Food and Drug Administration (FDA)'s registry of approved drug patents. This "patent thicket" delays the regulatory approval of competing products, and indirectly leads to higher healthcare costs. The US Federal Trade Commission (FTC) recently issued [a policy statement](#) warning that it would increase enforcement of improperly listed patents.

Description of the problem

According to the FTC, the pharmaceutical market has been distorted by improper patent listings for decades. The FDA's registry is intended to be used uniquely for active ingredients, but pharmaceutical companies list novel delivery methods. Pharmaceutical companies use these listings to prevent or delay the entry of potential competitors since listing automatically delays a competitor's FDA approval for up to thirty months. Investment in developing a competing product or a generic is disincentivized, increasing the time brand companies can profit from their product. These larger profits come at the expense of reducing patient access to more affordable prescription drugs and increasing costs to the healthcare system.

Results

In November 2023, the FTC warned ten major companies that their patents were improperly listed and over 100 patents were targeted. On April 30th 2024, the FTC challenged an additional 300 patents, across 20 products, including Novo-Nordisk's Ozempic and Amphastar's glucagon nasal inhaler. The targeted companies have a month to either withdraw or amend the disputed patent listings or confirm that these patents comply with legal requirements. The FTC also retains the right to start legal proceedings for "unfair methods of competition" or "illegal monopolization."

Lessons learned

In response to the first round of challenges, several improperly listed patents were removed. AstraZeneca, Boehringer Ingelheim and GSK announced out-of-pocket price caps for their asthma and COPD inhalers. While these price changes help consumers, they do not address the legal barriers to innovation. While Canada has similar pharmaceutical patent listing regulations, pharmaceutical patent thickets appear to be unique to the US. If antitrust enforcement were desired, Canadian policy-makers would have to amend the [Patented Medicines \(Notice of Compliance\) Regulations](#) to only include active ingredients and not drug delivery methods as is currently the case.